

Additional file 5. Sequences of the oligonucleotides used in this study.

Gen	Name	Sequence (5' to 3')
<i>Gsdma</i>	FM1_Gsdma	GAAGGAAGTTCATATTGATCC
	RM1_Gsdma	ACTGGACTTAACTTCTCCAC
<i>Gsdme</i>	FM1_Dfna5	CCTGTTTGATGAAGAACTCC
	RM1_Dfna5	CTCTCCTTGTATCCTGTATCC
<i>Gsdmd</i>	FM1_Gsdmd	GCTCTAAATGGGATATCCTTC
	RM1_Gsdmd	AATTCCTCCTCATCAATCCC
<i>Gsdmc</i>	FM1_Gsdmc	CCATCTAGATTTTCATGTGCC
	RM1_Gsdmc	ATACAGAACATCCCTGTCAC
<i>Pjvk</i>	FM1_Dfnb59	CTTCGAAAGAAACAGGAGAG
	RM1_Dfnb59	GTCGTAGAAGTCAGAAAAGAG
<i>Il1b</i>	FM2_Il1b	GTGATATTCTCCATGAGCTTTG
	RM2_Il1b	TCTTCTTTGGGTATTGCTTG
<i>Il6</i>	FM1_Il6	AAGAAATGATGGATGCTACC
	RM1_Il6	GAGTTTCTGTATCTCTCTGAAG
<i>Hprt1</i>	FM1_Hprt1	AGGGATTTGAATCACACGTTTG
	RM1_Hprt1	TTTACTGGCAACATCAACAG